

The emotional response to art and design work - empirical studies

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Abstract

The perception of drawing and design work involves an emotional response. We all know what we like and what we don't like. However when asked to articulate why we like a particular drawing this is not always easy. Designers and design educators may talk about "good" colour and "sensitive" mark-making but what is meant by these terms?

Many students will say that appreciation of art and design work is highly subjective; that what one person considers "good" will depend on personal preferences and may differ considerably from what another considers to be "good". However observations of design students would appear to indicate that the best work by students is generally recognised to be so by everyone in the group; there appears to be a "wow" factor that really excellent work evokes and no matter what someone's personal preferences may be they will recognise high quality work. Equally, very poor work will be identified, although there is often a reluctance by students to articulate this.

The emotional response to products and artifacts is now being recognised as a key driver in product acquisition, and a better understanding of how we respond is therefore of great importance to designers and manufacturers alike. Don Norman in his book "Emotional Design" (2004) talks of three levels of response to a design - visceral, behavioural and reflective. Patrick Jordan in "Designing Pleasurable Products" (2000) explains how good design can appeal to the user holistically, leading to products that that are a joy to own and use.

Current research at The University of Manchester is investigating response to initial artwork and drawing – the starting point for most design. Observations of responses to art and design work over the years indicate that these responses are more than merely subjective. The research programme at Manchester aims to investigate whether or not this is actually the case. Is “good” drawing really recognised to be so by a majority and can this be corroborated by experimental data? The work is also investigating the language used to describe the quality of art and design work; what exactly is meant by “good” and “sensitive” when describing the elements (line, shape, colour etc) that go to make up any drawing or design?

Initial experiments have taken sets of drawings of simple arrangements of natural objects and asked a wide range of people to describe the sets and then rank the drawings in terms of perceived quality. The responses to the work were recorded via questionnaires and observation, analysed and evaluated. Initial results suggest that there is indeed a consensus among observers when presented with sets of drawings as to which are “better” than others. Even with very abstract, non-representational artwork there appears to be consensus on those that appeal and those that don’t. With regard to articulating responses to drawing quality, respondents find this difficult; in the first experiment several felt unable to describe the drawings at all and many voiced their reluctance to describe the drawings verbally.

This paper outlines the experiments, analyses the data recorded and evaluates the work. The results give a greater insight to the immediate response to artwork and design and should be of particular interest to students and teachers of design and practicing designers.

Keywords: Drawing, quality, emotional response, language

Introduction

The language used when making judgements about art and design work is difficult. While we may know why we prefer one drawing to another we can't always explain why. Saying something is 'good' or 'better' may be all we can manage, but what is it that makes one drawing better than another. If mark making is described as being 'sensitive' what exactly do we mean by this?

Observations of students at The University of Manchester would suggest that high quality work is recognised by everyone, whatever their personal preferences with truly excellent work eliciting a 'wow' response.

This type of visceral emotional response is now recognised as a key driver in consumer purchase decisions. Three levels of response to a design - visceral, behavioural and reflective are described by Don Norman in his book 'Emotional Design' (2004) while Patrick Jordan explains how design must appeal in a more holistic manner in 'Designing Pleasurable Products' (2000). Designers are being forced to consider less tangible factors when designing. Technical and aesthetic factors alone are not enough and the key to the success of future designs will be the perceived benefits of ownership. This is what will drive widespread adoption.

The on-going research study described in this paper attempts to investigate perceptions of quality in artwork to gain a better understanding of emotional response.

The beginning – initial research questions

Responses to art and design work appear to be more than merely subjective. A number of initial research questions were identified:

- Is good drawing recognisable?
- Is there general agreement among a group of observers on what is 'good' and 'bad' drawing?
- What language is used to describe art and design work?
- Is there agreement in language use?

Some simple experiments were devised to investigate whether or not the view that good drawing would be recognised by a majority was actually true and could be corroborated by experimental data. The initial experiment which aimed to identify whether observers can agree which drawings are 'better' than others and to identify any common language used to describe the drawing quality.

The initial experiment

A simple pilot experiment was set up in which sets of drawings were viewed by observers and scored. Observers were also asked to say what they felt about the work. Responses were given via a questionnaire as this was considered an efficient and effective way of getting data which could be analysed both quantitatively and qualitatively.

Before drawings were selected it was necessary to define exactly what was meant by 'drawing' for the purpose of this experiment. The Oxford English Dictionary defines the noun 'drawing' as a 'monochrome picture or diagram made with a pencil, pen, or crayon rather than paint; the art or skill of making such pictures'. The definition given by the Penguin English Dictionary of the verb 'to draw' is 'to produce (a picture, diagram etc) by making lines on a surface; to produce a likeness of (somebody or something) in this way'.

From these dictionary definitions drawing involves pictures or diagrams, skill, lines and likeness and would normally not involve paint. The definition of drawing for this study is however somewhat broader and is 'artwork produced by mark making which can be in monochrome or colour, and in any medium'.

Selection of drawings

For the first experiment sets of drawings by both first and second year students were used. Each set showed the work of a single student to minimise any sense of competition between individuals.

At the time the research started first year textile design students had recently drawn simple arrangements of natural objects using different media and in different ways. Second year students had also recently completed a project which had involved them in producing drawing on a natural theme. Sets of these drawings were considered ideal for this first experiment for two main reasons. Firstly that is natural objects were felt to have no negative

connotations and secondly sets of drawings were required that were similar in many respects.

In total twelve sets of drawings, with three drawings in each set were collected. Six sets were of first year drawings and six from the second year group. The drawings were scanned into a computer and resized so that each image was similar in size. Each image was then posted on its own page in a PowerPoint presentation. The illustrations that follow show typical sets of drawings from first and second years.

Figure 1 – A set of first year drawings

Figure 2 – A set of second year drawings

The questionnaire

A questionnaire was designed which asked respondents to rate the drawings from 1 to 6 (with 1 being low quality and 6 high quality). Additionally respondents were asked to describe in 5 words or less the quality of the drawings. The questionnaire layout was deliberately kept simple.

A total of 51 respondents completed the questionnaire. The respondents were first and second year textile design students and a wide range of staff in and visitors to Textiles and Paper.

Data analysis

The background information and the drawing scores for every respondent were entered on to a spreadsheet. A count of the language used to describe the drawings was also undertaken and entered onto a spreadsheet.

The total scores for the drawings were established and analysed. There was a good spread of scores and these were put into a graph – see figure 3. The drawings are arranged in sets (1-12) from left to right on the x axis. The scores for each drawing are given on the y axis. From the graph it can be seen that all three drawings in set 4 (a,b,c) rated significantly higher than all other drawings while drawings 7b, 7c, 12b and 12c rated significantly lower.

Figure 3 – Total scores for the drawings

Figure 4 - Drawing set 4

Figure 5 - Drawing set 7

Figure 6 - Drawing set 12

The five drawings with the highest scores (4a, 4b, 4c, 9b and 11c) and the five with the lowest scores (7b, 7c, 10c, 12b and 12c) were identified. The modes and total scores for these drawings were studied and the words used to describe them were analysed. The results for three of the highest scoring drawings and for three of the lowest scoring drawings are detailed below.

Figure 7 - Respondent scores for drawing 4a

For drawing 4a, the average (mean) was 4.33, mode 4 and median 4. Only eight people scored this drawing less than the mode, 43 (86%) scored the mode or higher. For this drawing there certainly appears to be a high degree of consensus with regard to quality.

Figure 8 - Respondent scores for drawing 9b

For drawing 9b, the average (mean) was 3.94, mode 4 and median 4. Fourteen people scored this drawing less than 4 (the mode and mean), thirty seven scored it 4 or higher. For this drawing, while there is less degree of consensus with regard to quality, 72 % still scored it at the mode level or higher.

Figure 9 - Respondent scores for drawing 11c

For drawing 11c, the average (mean) was 3.82, mode 4 and median 4. Eighteen people scored this drawing less than 4 (the mode and mean), thirty three scored it 4 or higher. For this drawing while again there is less degree of consensus with regard to quality nearly twice as many, 66% scored it at 4 or higher.

Figure 10 - Respondent scores for drawing 7b

For drawing 7b, the average (mean) was 2.16, 1 and 2 were both scored 18 times (the mode), and the median was 2. While fifteen people scored this drawing higher than two, thirty six (72%) scored two or less. Only eight scored higher than 3, six scoring 4, one scoring 5 and one 6.

Figure 11 - Respondent scores for drawing 10c

For drawing 10c, the average (mean) was 2.14, mode 2 and median 2. Fourteen people scored this drawing higher than 2 while thirty seven (74%) scored 2 or less. Only 2 scored higher than 3, one scoring 4 and one 5.

Figure 12 - Respondent scores for drawing 12c

For drawing 12c, the average (mean) was 2.2, mode 2 and median 2. Twenty people scored this drawing higher than 2 with thirty one (62%) scoring it at 2 or below. While there appeared to be less agreement with the responses for this drawing no one gave it more than 4 and then only three people did that.

Overall when the data was initially analysed there appeared to be a significant degree of consensus. For the high scoring drawings a high percentage of respondents agreed, at least 66%. For the lower scoring drawings there was less consensus. Interestingly for the higher scoring drawings there was a greater consensus; this may relate back to the reluctance to give negative comments that had been noted in observations of students previously.

Language analysis

A count of the language used to describe the drawings was also undertaken and entered onto a spreadsheet. A large spread of words was used with over 100 used more than once, 37 used more than five times and twenty used more than ten times. Popular words were detail, lines, shading, textural and tonal although these are not descriptors of drawing quality. The most used word by far was good.

The 37 most frequently used words were grouped into negative, positive and neutral words. There were 11 words that could be considered positive, 11 negative words and 15 that were neutral (neither positive or negative), which could be both negative or positive, or which related to design elements and were nouns rather than quality descriptors.

Figure 13 - Negative words with usage

Figure 14 – Positive words with usage

The graph that follows shows the number of words used more than ten times. These words have been categorised as positive, negative or neutral.

Figure 15 – Words used more than ten times

Five negative words were used more than ten times and in total these were identified as being used on 64 occasions. Six words that were considered to be positive were used 161 times, nine neutral words were identified and these were used 233 times. Again there appears to be a reluctance to make negative comments and there is a marked tendency for neutral comments (neither positive or negative) to be used.

Observations on the first experiment

Having carried out an initial analysis of the results it was felt that there was some agreement from observers as to which drawings are ‘better’ than others. The three drawings in set 4 were clearly rated as ‘better’ than the others. Interestingly on average respondents with art and design degrees rated this set lower than the other respondents.

With regard to a common language: from the words used several were identified as being used more than ten and some more than ten times. ‘Good’ was by far the most popular but it is rather a bland descriptor. Further research into just what is meant by ‘good’ is required.

There were some problems with the responses. Several people did not give words to describe the drawings while others voiced reluctance to describe the drawings verbally. On the other hand many people used more than five words to describe drawings. This backs up the

perception that articulating responses to drawing quality is difficult; respondents struggle, miss out this part of the questionnaire, or give a lot of words, perhaps because they find it difficult to clearly describe in words what they feel.

The personal data that was given was sometimes clearly wrong; several 19 year olds already claimed to have university degrees!

Many respondents reported finding the task difficult and this may be why some people took an extremely long time to fill in the questionnaire.

For further experiments several aspects need more consideration.

- Did the order the drawings were presented in have an impact on the results?
- Many respondents said they wanted to see the originals rather than images on a computer.
- With regard to language it may be helpful to give respondents a set of descriptors to choose from and also a list of what we want them to describe – design elements and principles.
- Images –the images were chosen from what was available within two student projects.

For a future experiment drawings could be:

- by well-known artists rather than students;
- produced specifically for the experiment;
- pre-ranked rather than random.
- Many more respondents are needed and wider ranges of age and background are required.
- An electronic questionnaire could be used so it could be:
 - accessed via the web;
 - more easily analysed.
- Respondents could be asked for more information such as why they find it difficult to describe the quality of drawings in words.

For this initial experiment the aims were to identify whether observers can agree which drawings are 'better' than others and to identify common language used to describe the

drawing quality. The results suggest that observers can agree which drawings are ‘better’ than others and that common language used to describe drawing quality can be identified.

Further analysis of the results

Further analysis of the results of the first experiment identified a number of sets of drawings where there was a significant difference in overall score for two of the drawings. The data for these sets was considered in more detail.

The sets identified were:

- set 1 a and c , set 2 a and b, set 3 a and c, set 7 a and c, set 8 a and b
- set 9 a and b, set 10 a and c, set 11 a and c and set 12 a and c.

For each of these sets the 51 respondents scores were entered onto graphs. These graphs were analysed to see how many scored the first drawing from each set higher than the second, how many scored the drawings equally and how many respondents scored the second drawing higher than the first. The results are tabled below.

	Set 1	Set 2	Set 3	Set 7	Set 8	Set 9	Set 10	Set 11	Set 12
number of people scoring the first drawing higher than the second	28	31	14	31	13	1	24	8	25
number of people scoring the first drawing =second	16	13	9	19	7	11	13	11	21
number of people scoring the first drawing lower than second	7	7	28	1	31	39	14	32	5

Table 1

These results were put into graph formats. Graph 1 shows the sets along the x axis where the blue columns show the number of people scoring the first drawing from each set higher than the second, the pink column showing the number of people scoring both drawings in the set the same and the yellow column showing the number of people scoring the second drawing from the set higher than the first.

Figure 16

The next graph (figure 17) shows similar data as above but the bars are coloured to indicate drawings belonging to the same set and the number of respondents scoring the two drawings the same in the sets is not included. The left hand column for each set shows the number for those scoring the first drawing in the set higher than the second and the right column shows the number of respondents scoring the second drawing higher than the first.

Figure 17

The graph in figure 18 shows the overall scores of the drawings selected for further study. It is clear that the graph in figure 17 and the one in figure 18 follow a similar pattern.

Figure 18

From this further data analysis outlined above it appears that there is a definite consensus by a significant number of the respondents as to which drawing is better.

The second experiment

A second experiment was conducted to see whether or not the results of the first experiment could be replicated.

This time the sets of drawings that the respondents were asked to rate were those that had been selected for further study above by virtue of the fact that there was a significant difference in overall score for two of the drawings. These twelve sets of two drawings were presented to respondents via a PowerPoint presentation in a similar way to the first experiment. This time however, rather than rate the drawings respondents were asked via a questionnaire indicate the drawing that they felt was better in terms of drawing.

There were 24 respondents for this second experiment. They were a group of first year students, not the group whose drawings had been used, and quite deliberately a group who had not taken part in the first experiment. The graph (figure 19) showing the result of this second experiment is shown below. The overall pattern of this graph quite clearly echoes that of figure 18 which shows the overall scores for the same 12 sets from the first experiment.

Figure 19

In conclusion and the future

The work to date would indicate quite clearly that the view that ‘good’ quality drawing can be identified consistently by a range of respondents. We now need to investigate whether there are differences in respondents’ responses with regard to age, education and other factors. More work is scheduled to look at language use and further experiments taking into account the observations from the first set of experiments are currently being designed.

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